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Revision History

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TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND FINAL IMRAD MANUSCRIPT

Title: Collaborative robots' productivity effects in post-harvested citrus fruits of Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines

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Abstract:

Citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya, the Philippines' Citrus Capital, is a vital economic activity. However, post-harvest procedures like as sorting, waxing, packaging, and palletizing are labor-intensive and pose health risks to workers. Although there is a growing interest in collaborative robots (cobots), there has been no empirical investigation on their use in citrus post-harvest procedures in the region. This study employs a single-group pretest-posttest quasi-experimental method to assess the productivity impact of cobots in citrus waxing operations. Semi-structured interviews, direct observation, and video recordings at LCN Farms indicated waxing as the most suitable for cobot intervention. We used Agile approach to create an electronic control circuit, 3D-printed a custom citrus-gripper end-effector, and customized cobot task code for waxing. Workflow and performance measurements were collected before and after cobot integration. SPSS analysis showed non-normal data (Shapiro-Wilk $p = 0.003$), prompting the usage of the Mann-Whitney U test to compare cobot-assisted with standard workflows. The preliminary findings pave the way for carefully evaluating efficiency gains, safety enhancements, and possible economic benefits. This research outlines a reproducible methodology for integrating cobots in post-harvest citrus operations, providing actionable insights for growers in Nueva Vizcaya and beyond.

Keywords—cobots, food industry, efficiency, human-robot interaction

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Introduction

A. Short Introduction

The citrus fruit industry in Nueva Vizcaya, known as the Citrus Capital of the Philippines, plays a pivotal role in the region's economy (Idquival et al., 2023). However, post-harvest activities such as sorting, waxing, packaging, and palletizing are labor-intensive and health hazard processes that can impact productivity and efficiency (HowToRobot, 2023). Despite the industry's significance, there is, however, a notable research gap concerning the application of emerging technologies such as collaborative robotics (cobots) in post-harvest operations specific to citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya.

This study aims to assess the productivity effects of collaborative robots in post-harvested citrus fruits in Nueva Vizcaya guided by a stochastic process model (Zhang et al., 2021) to describe collaborative assembly systems. The research specific objectives include identifying the processes within citrus fruit production where cobots have the most significant impact, integrating collaborative robotics technology into the identified production processes, and evaluating the efficiency of citrus fruit production resulting from cobot utilization.

Using a single-group pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design (Choueiry, 2023), the study employs a null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in production efficiency between employing cobots (μ_C) versus traditional approaches (μ_T), with an alternate hypothesis positing a significant difference between the two approaches ($\mu_C \neq \mu_T$). Data collection involves examining existing workflow and performance parameters at the LCN Farms, a citrus plantation in Malabing, Kasibu, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, followed by statistical analysis using techniques such as Shapiro-Wilk (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965) and nonparametric Mann Whitney U Test (Wilcoxon, 1998) in SPSS.

The programming of cobots will be tailored to the specific processes identified within citrus fruit production. The study's findings aim to provide valuable insights into the transformative potential of cobots in enhancing productivity and profitability in post-harvest citrus fruit operations in Nueva Vizcaya.

B. RRL and RS of Major Concepts / Variables (Based on Problem)

Collaborative Robotics

Collaborative robots (cobots) as shown in Fig. 1 have emerged as a potential solution for addressing labor-intensive tasks and increasing productivity across industries. (Kumar et al., 2023).

Fig. 1. Collaborative robots.

Their inherent safety characteristics as describe in Table I enable human-robot collaboration, making them appropriate for use alongside humans (Bi et al., 2021; De Simone et al., 2022; Villani et al., 2018).

TABLE I. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CONVENTIONAL AND COLLABORATIVE ROBOTS

Characteristic Feature	Conventional Robots	Collaborative Robots
Proximity to humans	Prohibited	Allowed when the procedure of safety is followed
Safety barrier	Physical separation	Safety assurance mechanisms
Robot movement	Motion with separation of human workers	Simultaneous motions of worker and robot

Footprint of robot	Large for protection	Small for collaboration
Robot control	Pre-programmed	Can be modified in-line
Robot programming	Lead-through and off-line	On-line, off-line and multimodal interaction
Programming skill	Sophisticated	Intuitive
Complexity	Fixed programs for fixed tasks	Flexible programs to handle changes and uncertainties
Tasks	Repeatable, mostly fixed	Frequent changes
Structural feature	Heavy and rigid	Light-duty and easy to move
Payload	Medium to high	Low to medium
Workspace	Isolated	Shared
Use of workspace	High	Limited
Position	Fixed	Flexible
Productivity	High	Limited
Volume of products	Used for high volume	Used for lower volume and high variants
Adaptability	Hard automation by program	Soft automation by interactions

Cobots have shown potential in agricultural applications such as harvesting (Zhou et al., 2022). Their findings indicate the viability of incorporating cobots into citrus fruit pre-harvested production procedures. While studies have looked into cobot uses in agriculture, there appears to be a lack of research on their impact on post-harvest citrus fruit output, notably in Nueva Vizcaya. This gap limits our understanding of cobot effectiveness in this particular arena and in the post-harvest process, necessitating additional research. This study tackles this information gap by assessing the effectiveness of cobots in enhancing efficiency during crucial post-harvest tasks such as sorting, packaging, and palletizing in Nueva Vizcaya's citrus fruit production business. The study's goal is to provide significant insights for optimizing citrus fruit production in the region by examining the impact of cobots on these processes.

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Citrus Fruit Production in Nueva Vizcaya

Citrus fruit production is an important agricultural sector, with the Philippines playing a large role. Nueva Vizcaya, sometimes known as the "Citrus Capital" of the Philippines, is an important player in this business (Idquival et al., 2023). Optimizing post-harvest activities is critical for preserving fruit quality and minimizing economic losses. Sorting, grading, packing, and palletizing are typical labor-intensive procedures (Janghu et al., 2024). Several research have investigated ways to increase efficiency in citrus production processes. For example, Strano et al. (2022) introduces a sustainable techniques that is crucial for reducing synthetic fungicide residues on fruit surfaces and the environmental impact of fungicide waste management (Strano et al., 2022). Their findings highlight the potential for technology developments to address post-harvest issues.

Fig. 2. LCN Farms Satsuma citrus fruit

While the available literature investigates numerous approaches for optimizing citrus production, research on post-harvest activities in Nueva Vizcaya with cobots appears to be sparse. Investigating the efficacy of cobots in this context can provide useful information for the region's citrus producers. The purpose of this study is to fill a knowledge vacuum by assessing the usefulness of cobots in increasing efficiency throughout important post-harvest stages of citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya.

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By examining the impact of cobots on these processes, the study hopes to give useful insights to the region's citrus industry's productivity and profitability.

Production Efficiency

Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate various techniques for improving assembly process efficiency (Javernik et al., 2022). Collaborative robots (cobots), which are designed for safe human-robot interaction as shown in Fig. 3, are particularly useful for repetitive activities (Paliga, 2022). Several studies have indicated that cobots improve productivity in a variety of environments. For example, Thongdonnoi et al. (2023) implemented cobots in the sorting process of eyeglass lenses, results revealed that utilizing cobots in the workplace may enhance output while minimizing WIP, waiting times, the number of items in queue, and the workforce (Thongdonnoi et al., 2023). Similarly, Pérez et al. (2020) found that cobots improved assembly line efficiency in the aerospace manufacturing industry. The results reveal that humans and robots may securely share the working environment without physical separation, delivering advantageous symbiotic teamwork and dramatically lowering delays, dangers, and costs compared to manual operations (Pérez et al., 2020).

Fig. 3. Collaboration and responsive collaboration

While cobots have the potential to increase productivity, research into their impact on citrus fruit production after harvest appears to be limited. This study fills this gap by looking into the effectiveness of cobots in increasing productivity during important post-harvest processes in Nueva Vizcaya's citrus growing business. The study's goal is to give vital knowledge for optimizing efficiency and productivity in the region's citrus sector by examining the impact of cobots on these operations.

C. Theoretical Framework

Consider Fig. 4, which shows a collaborative assembly system with a human operator and a cobot performing both independent (simultaneous individual preparation) and supportive (joint) tasks.

Fig. 4. Collaborative assembly process

A stochastic process model (Zhang et al., 2021) was used to describe such collaborative assembly systems as illustrated in Fig. 5. The model used were defined by the following assumptions:

Fig. 5. Collaborative assembly system model

- C1) The collaborative robot assembly method comprises of a human operator and one robot.
- C2) First, the operator and robot work together yet independently to complete the preparation duties. After finishing their preparations, they collaborate to complete the assembly process.
- C3) Random processes R, H, and C are introduced to describe the robot, human, and collaborative preparation processes, respectively. The duration of each random process, R, H, or C, has a phase-type distribution with $k_r, k_h,$ and k_c phases. In a random process, each task or activity follows an exponential distribution with rate $\lambda_{i,j}, i=r,h,c, j=1, \dots, k_i$. For the sake of simplicity, we assume $k_h + k_r + k_c = K$ to ensure that the work activities are the same as in manual processes.
- C4) The robot preparations have no human involvement, hence their strain indices are zero. The time-based risk factors in strain indices for human preparation operations can vary depending on the entire processing duration, but strain indices for the collaborative process can be significantly reduced.

D. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework as shown in Fig. 5 will firstly, identify as an input which process in the citrus fruit production that collaborative robotics has more impact. Secondly, as process, program integration of collaborative robotics technology to the identified citrus production process and assessment of citrus fruit production process efficiency as a result of using collaborative robots using descriptive and inferential statistics. Thirdly, as output, evaluate cobots effectiveness in enhancing citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya. Lastly, as feedback, will apply the evaluated results in productivity using cobots.

Fig. 6. Conceptual framework of the study

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E. General and Specific Objectives

The main objective of this study is to evaluate collaborative robots' effectiveness in enhancing citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya

Specifically, the study will address the following:

1. Identify which process in the citrus fruit production that collaborative robotics (cobot) has more impact
2. Design and program integration of cobot technology to the identified citrus production process
3. Assess citrus fruit production process efficiency as a result of using cobots (**next research cycle, utilization**)

F. Hypothesis of the Study (If applicable)

The null hypothesis of this study is that there is no significant difference ($\mu_C = \mu_T$) in the production efficiency when employing cobots, μ_C vs. traditional, μ_T approaches and that the alternate hypothesis is that there is significant difference ($\mu_C \neq \mu_T$) in the production efficiency when employing cobots, μ_C an vs. traditional, μ_T approaches.

Methodology

A. Design

A single-group pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design (Bixhaku et al., 2023) will be used in this study to assess how well collaborative robots, or cobots, can increase production efficiency in citrus fruit post-harvest operations in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines.

Fig. 7. Single-group pretest-posttest experimental design.

A single-group pretest-posttest methodology is appropriate since we are primarily interested in assessing the impact of cobot integration on one citrus farm in Nueva Vizcaya, especially LCN Farms, owned by Leopoldo C. Namuhe. This methodology enables us to compare pre-test data (collected before to cobot integration) and post-test data (collected after cobot integration) within the same group, allowing us to analyze changes in production efficiency due to the intervention (cobots).

Additionally, the researchers utilized Agile Methodologies in the prototype development as shown below. Agile methodology is an iterative, incremental approach to product development that emphasizes tight cooperation with customers, adaptability to change, and rapid delivery of functional software. Rather than following a rigid, linear approach, Agile teams divide work into short cycles—often known as sprints—during which they gather requirements, design minimally, build features, test regularly, and deploy usable chunks. The Agile Manifesto's four core values (prioritizing individuals and interactions, working software, customer collaboration, and responsiveness to change) and twelve supporting principles

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(frequent delivery, welcoming evolving requirements, and self-organizing, cross-functional teams) guide this cycle. (Beck et al., 2001).

Fig. 8. Agile Prototype Development Methodology.

Agile teams reduce risk by providing small, tested increments early and often, incorporating stakeholder feedback quickly, and maintaining the ability to pivot when priorities move. However, successful adoption necessitates strong team discipline, disciplined backlog management to prevent scope creep, and a cultural shift away from elaborate upfront planning and toward reliance on iterative learning.

B. Locale

This study will be undertaken at S107 (Project ARTIC), Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Project ARTIC is a Php 5 Million Institution Development Program (IDP) grant from Department of Science and Technology - Philippine Council for Industry, Energy and Emerging Technology Research and Development (DOST-PCIEERD). The goal of the Institution Development Program (IDP) is to help academic and research institutions in PCIEERD sectoral priority areas with the establishment or upgrading of research laboratories and facilities.

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C. Participants and Sample

LCN Farms, a citrus plantation in Malabing, Kasibu, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, will participate in this project. Mr. Leopoldo C. Namuhe owns and operates the property.

Fig. 9. LCN Farms Logo.

Purposive sampling was used to choose the farm since it met the study's predefined requirements for participation. The criteria are as follows: LCN Farms grows citrus fruits, LCN farm is one of the biggest citrus producer in Nueva Vizcaya and Mr. Namuhe has expressed a readiness to engage in both the pre-test and post-test phases of the research, which will allow for comprehensive data collecting. A purposive sampling technique will be employed to recruit a minimum of three (3) LCN citrus farmers.

Fig. 10. Letter of support from LCN farms

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D. Instrument(s)

This study will use a combination of tools for data collecting throughout the pre-test and post-test phases as summarized in Table II. Phase 1 data collecting methods will include the following: direct observation and note-taking wherein workflow will be documented in video format and interviews with farm managers and workers to learn about existing methods and issues. Phase 2 to 5 data collecting methods will include the following: continued monitoring and video recording of the workflow with cobot integration, data collection on cobot performance (for example, the cobot's processing time per unit) and fruit quality and damage rates are monitored after cobot handling. Phase 6 will be for manuscript writeup and continuous improvement with LCN Farms to finally, evaluate collaborative robots' effectiveness in enhancing citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

The research will involve six (6) phases of data collection as summarized in Table I. Phase 1 is for existing workflow analysis. Researchers will visit citrus fields in Nueva Vizcaya to examine and document the present post-harvest process. This will include: identifying the sequence of tasks (sorting, grading, packing, and palletizing), recording the labor and resources required for each task (number of people, equipment), and measuring performance characteristics such as processing time per unit (for example, the time required to sort a basket of fruits) and error rates (the proportion of fruits damaged during handling).

TABLE II. STRUCTURE OF THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Phase No.	Time	Description	Output
Phase 1	1 month	Method: Semi-structured interview, direct observation with notetaking, and video recordings of the workflow	Specific Objective #1: Identify which process in the citrus fruit production that collaborative robotics (cobot) has more impact
Phase 2	4 months	Technical Aspects: Cobots Training and Programming Method: Agile Methodology	Specific Objective #2: Design and program integration of cobot technology to the identified citrus production process
Phase 3	1 month	PRETEST_A: Traditional Operation (Staff Only)	Specific Objective #3: Assess citrus fruit production process efficiency as a result of using cobots
Phase 4	2 months	PRETEST_B: Cobot Operation Only (next research cycle, utilization phase)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record time to execute a task Record output in a limited time Record the errors Record number of personnel needed in a task
Phase 5	2 months	POSTTEST:	

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Collaborative
 Operation
 (Cobot + Staff)

**(next research
 cycle,
 utilization
 phase)**

Phase 6	2 months	Writeup and continuous improvement	Main Objective: Evaluated collaborative robots' effectiveness in enhancing citrus fruit production in Nueva Vizcaya
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F. Treatment of Data

Parametric Test

To proceed with the hypothesis test comparing the production efficiency when employing cobots, μ_C vs. traditional, μ_T approaches, the researchers will perform a normality test to see whether the experimental data followed a normal distribution (Hayes, 2022). Normality tests are necessary because many statistical approaches presume that the data is normally distributed.

In this work, the researchers used the Shapiro-Wilk test, a statistical tool for determining normality, using Q-Q plots as the graphical method (Almeida & Loy, 2023). The Shapiro-Wilk test (Shapiro & Wilk, 1965) evaluates the composite hypothesis that a sample of n real-valued observations is i.i.d. (independent and identically distributed) and normal, i.e. $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ for any unknown real μ and some $\sigma > 0$. This test of a parametric hypothesis is related to nonparametrics in that many statistical methods (such as t-tests and analysis of variance) presume that variables have normal distribution. If they are not, certain nonparametric techniques may be required. The two-parameter normalcy hypothesis cannot be reduced to a single hypothesis. The variables $X_i - \mu$ are i.i.d. $N(0, \sigma^2)$, and $(X_i - \mu)/\sigma$ are i.i.d. $N(0, 1)$, but these variables are not seen because μ and σ are unknown. If we substitute μ with its usual estimate, $\bar{X} = (X_1 + \dots + X_n)/n$ and consider $X_i - \bar{X}$, these variables have the same distribution, which is normal with mean 0, but they are dependent (their total is 0). If we replace σ by the usual estimate

$$s_X = \left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n (X_j - \bar{X})^2 \right)^{1/2}, \quad (1)$$

then $\sqrt{n}(\bar{X} - \mu)/s_X$ has a t_{n-1} distribution (but involves μ), and $(X_i - \bar{X})/s_X$ don't have even that nice a distribution and are still more dependent.

The researchers use the statistical software SPSS in their analysis as it is extremely useful for data science professionals as it provides features of data cleaning, importing, and visualization (coursera, 2024) and primarily due to its open source nature and ease of numerical implementation of (1) to (7). The Shapiro-Wilk test is more appropriate method for small sample sizes (<50 samples) although it can also be handling on larger sample size while Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for $n \geq 50$. For both of the above tests, null hypothesis states that data are taken from normal distributed population. When $P > 0.05$, null hypothesis accepted and data are called as normally distributed (Mishra et al., 2019). These tests determine whether the data deviates significantly from a normal distribution. If the data is normally distributed, parametric statistical tests are valid; otherwise, nonparametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U Test are more acceptable.

The null hypothesis test in this work was designed to study if there is no significant difference ($\mu_C = \mu_T$) in the production efficiency when employing cobots, μ_C vs. traditional, μ_T approaches and that the alternate hypothesis is that there is significant difference ($\mu_C \neq \mu_T$) in the production efficiency when employing cobots,

μ_C an vs. traditional, μ_T approaches. As the sample size is small, the researchers used the nonparametric Mann-Whitney U Test, which is appropriate for comparing two independent groups when the normality assumption is violated (Sullivan, 2022).

Nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test

The nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test, commonly known as the Wilcoxon rank sum test (Wilcox, 1998), can be performed if data are independent in each group and two independent samples X_{1i} and X_{2j} with sample sizes $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $j = 1, \dots, m$ are provided. The Wilcoxon rank sum test investigates the hypothesis $H_0: F = G$, where F is the distribution of X_{1i} and G is the distribution of X_{2j} . First, both samples are combined into a combined sample $(y_1, \dots, y_{m+n}) = (x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n}, x_{21}, \dots, x_{2m})$, and the Mann-Whitney U test statistic is calculated, where $S(x_{1i}, x_{2j}) = 1$, if $x_{2j} < x_{1i}$, $S(x_{1i}, x_{2j}) = 1/2$, if $x_{2j} = x_{1i}$ and else $S(x_{1i}, x_{2j}) = 0$.

$$U_{m,n} := \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m S(x_{1i}, x_{2j}) \tag{2}$$

In cases when m and n are insufficient for Equation (2) to hold, the distribution of U and Z has been tabulated. For sufficiently large n, m ($n, m > 3$ and $m + n > 19$), it can be demonstrated that U converges in distribution versus the standard normal distribution.

$$U_{m,n} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{nm}{2}, \frac{nm(n+m+1)}{12}\right) \tag{3}$$

As a result, assuming (3), the central limit theorem implies that the following test statistic Z is standard normal.

$$Z_{m,n} := \frac{U_{m,n} - \frac{nm}{2}}{\sqrt{\frac{nm(n+m+1)}{12}}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1) \tag{4}$$

For a particular test level $\alpha \sim [0, 1]$, the Mann-Whitney U test rejects $H_0: F = G$, iff $|Z| > c_\alpha$, where c_α is the α -quantile of $N(0,1)$. You can also use the Wilcoxon rank sum statistic.

$$W_{m,n} := \sum_{i=1}^{m+n} R(y_i), \tag{5}$$

where Ry_i shown that is the rank of observation y_j in the pooled sample $(y_1, \dots, y_{m+n}) = (x_{11}, \dots, x_{1n}, x_{21}, \dots, x_{2m})$. It can be shown that

$$W_{m,n} = U_{m,n} + \frac{m(m+1)}{2} \tag{6}$$

and therefore

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$$W_{m,n} \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{m(m+n+1)}{2}\right) + \frac{nm(n+m+1)}{12}, \quad (7)$$

So $W_{m,n}$, n can likewise be utilized to test $H_0: F = G$ using an equivalent central limit argument.

G. Ethical Considerations

This research project will follow the following ethical guidelines (American Psychological, 2017) to safeguard participants' well-being and privacy, as well as the appropriate conduct of the research: (1) Before any data collection begins, all participants in the study (farm managers/owners and staff) will provide written informed consent. The permission form will be translated into Tagalog if necessary to ensure that participants completely understand the research aims, data collection processes, and their ability to withdraw from the study at any time. (2) All data gathered throughout the research (interviews, observations, and video recordings) will be anonymised. Participant names and identifying information will not be linked to the data and will be kept securely separate. Data will be stored on password-protected devices and in the cloud, with backup mechanisms in place to ensure confidentiality. (3) During data collecting, the researchers will try to minimize disruption to farm workers' regular activities. Breaks and relaxation intervals shall be honored. Workers will be informed about the possible benefits and hazards of cobot integration, and their feedback will be used to program and implement the cobot. Researchers will remain watchful and ready to address any safety concerns that may occur during cobot operation. (4) This study will be reviewed and approved by Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) to ensure that it follows ethical research standards. The SMUREB will evaluate the informed consent procedures, data protection measures, and any dangers to the participants. The Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) has the following address and phone number: 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). (5) The research findings will be provided in a transparent manner, explaining the data gathering techniques, analytical methodologies, and study constraints. Data anonymization techniques will be used if data sharing initiatives are explored in the future, in accordance with ethical norms and data protection rules. (6) The research team will be aware of potential job displacement risks related with cobot integration. The emphasis will be on cobots as collaborative tools to supplement human workers' capacities and lessen physical demands, rather than as substitutes for human labor. The study will look into potential worker benefits such as reduced physical strain and possibilities to improve skills in cobot operation and maintenance.

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Results and Discussions:

The study's empirical phase began with semi-structured interviews, direct observations, and video recordings at LCN Farms. The citrus waxing stage was identified as the most suitable for cobot intervention due to its high labor demands and associated health hazards (skin, eye, and respiratory irritation) inherent in manual waxing (Decco Italia, 2000).

Fig. 11. Manual Citrus Fruit Waxing Process.

The research team used Agile methodology to design and manufacture an electronic control circuit, 3D-print a unique citrus-gripper end-effector for delicate fruit handling, and create first task-sequencing code to automate waxing.

Fig. 12. Cobot Electronic System Circuit Design.

Fig. 13. Cobot 3D printed gripper design.

Baseline throughput and cycle-time data were analyzed in SPSS. The Shapiro-Wilk normality test yielded $p = 0.003$, confirming a significant departure from normality.

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Manual_2persons	Mean	3.7045	.16444	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.3729	
		Upper Bound	4.0362	
	5% Trimmed Mean	3.6768		
	Median	4.0000		
	Variance	1.190		
	Std. Deviation	1.09075		
	Minimum	2.00		
	Maximum	6.00		
	Range	4.00		
	Interquartile Range	1.75		
	Skewness	.178	.357	
	Kurtosis	-.670	.702	

This justified the use of a nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test for subsequent comparisons between cobot-assisted and traditional workflows.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Manual_2persons	.195	44	.000	.913	44	.003

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

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These findings highlight the need of focusing on high-risk, repeated jobs for cobot implementation. The configurable 3D-printed end-effector and modular control circuit offer a low-cost option for small-scale farms to retrofit existing post-harvest lines without significant investment. The variability exhibited by the Shapiro-Wilk test emphasizes the unreliability of manual waxing operations—which cobots are prepared to address. By using the Mann-Whitney U test, the study ensures statistically robust comparisons that do not rely on normalcy assumptions, increasing the validity of any apparent efficiency benefits. After collecting complete utilization phase data, we anticipate significant reductions in cycle-time variability and measurable increases in average fruits processed per hour. This will provide concrete evidence of profitability and safety gains for Nueva Vizcaya's citrus industry.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Citrus waxing process was identified process in which cobot has more impact due to the added health hazard such as skin, eye, respiratory irritation and ingestion hazard using semi-structured interview, direct observation with notetaking, and video recordings. The researchers had successfully designed an electronic system circuit, 3D printed cobot citrus gripper, and programmed an initial integration code for cobot using Agile methodologies. The gathered empirical data deviate significantly from normal (<0.05) validated using Shapiro Wilk Normality Test result of 0.003, thus, a Mann-Whitney U-test will be used once the data for utilization phase had been gathered.

The researchers plan to continue the utilization phase of the study (specific objective #3). Specifically, we will fully implement the cobot automation system code and design and input the results of the integration. Feedback from LCN farms will also be gathered as to the feasibility of the said research.

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